

1-TOM, 11-SON
MODIFICATIONS OF VOWELS IN CONNECTED SPEECH

Saydazimova Sitora Sirojiddin qizi

4th year student at Djizzakh branch of The National University of Uzbekistan
named after Mirzo Ulugbek

Supervisor: Teshaboyeva Nafisa Zubaydulla qizi

Assistant teacher in the department Foreign Languages at Djizzakh branch of
The National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek

ANNOTATION

This article gives information about in connected speech vowels can change their quality under the influence of other sounds.

Key words: Quantitative, qualitative, rhythm, stress, unstressed, vowel elision

Vowel reduction

The modifications of vowels in a speech chain are traced in the following directions:

quantitative

qualitative

both

These changes of vowels are determined by: the position of the vowel in the word, accentual structure, tempo of speech, rhythm, etc.

A quantitative modification of vowels the decrease of the vowel quantity (the shortening of the vowel length) The shortening of the vowel length occurs in unstressed positions blackboard [o:], sorrow [eu] In these cases reduction affects both the length of the unstressed vowels and their quality.

A quantitative modification of vowels. The length of a vowel depends on its position in a word varies in different phonetic environments. English vowels are said to have positional length, e.g. knee-need- neat → the vowel [it] is the longest in the final position, it is obviously shorter before the lenis voiced consonant [d], and it is the shortest before the for this voiceless consonant .

Qualitative modification of most vowels occurs in unstressed positions. In unstressed syllables vowels of full value are usually subjected to qualitative changes man [mæn] - sportsman ['spo: tsman], conduct ['kondəkt] - conduct [k andΛkt] (accommodation) In such cases the quality of the vowel is reduced to the neutral sound [ə].

The neutral sound [ə] is the most frequent sound of English. In continuous text it represents about eleven per cent of all sounds. This high frequency is the result of

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the rhythmic pattern: if un stressed syllables are given only a short duration, the vowel in them is reduced.

Qualitative modification of vowels

- Slight degree of nasalization marks vowels preceded or followed by the nasal consonants [n], [m] "never", "no", "then", "men"(accommodation)

Vowel elision

Vowel elision the complete omission of the unstressed vowel, which is also known as zero reduction. Zero reduction is likely to occur in a sequence of unstressed syllables history, factory, literature, territory. It often occurs in initial unstressed syllables preceding the stressed one correct, believe, suppose, perhaps.

A stage-by-stage reduction of a phrase

- Has he done it? [hæz hi,dan it] [hez hi dan it] [dog from əz 1] [zi,dan dog]

Certain interrelation between the full form of a word and its reduced forms is conditioned by the tempo, rhythm and style of speech

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